

The combined line planning modification and vehicle scheduling problem for a fleet of electric buses

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ABSTRACT

Transitioning from conventional public transport fleets to electric ones necessitates comprehensive strategic, tactical, and operational planning. To supplement the research work in this area, the current study focuses on the Combined Line Planning Modification and Electric Vehicle Scheduling Problem, addressing the complexities of integrating electric buses into existing transport networks. We introduce a two-stage approach for the solution of this problem. First, we schedule the fleet for each bus line for different possible layouts (options), that arise from the elimination of bus stops in the existing layout of the examined lines, taking into consideration the charging needs of the buses by solving the Electric Vehicle Scheduling Problem (E-VSP), which is solved as a mixed-integer quadratic program (MIQP). At this stage, the modeling takes into account the real-world timetables of the line, the autonomy of the buses, the number of trips performed per day, the trip distances, and the deadheading distances. All these essential parameters remain the same for all the examined modifications and are based on the data provided by the transport operator for the existing lines. Then, in a second stage, we examine which modification of each bus line is optimal, while considering the passengers' demand for each stop and the available fleet size, formulated as a mixed-integer linear program (MILP). The goal of the overall two-stage approach is to minimize the unserved passenger demand that arises from the possible modifications of bus lines and the number of required vehicles when transitioning to electromobility.

1. Introduction

Transportation is one of the largest sources of greenhouse gas emissions and energy consumption. Cities around the world aim to decrease carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions by switching from conventional vehicles to electric ones. The transition of public transport to electromobility is a key factor in reducing gas emissions. Several urban centers and public transport operators have launched the deployment of electric bus fleets in order to accomplish this. In 2021, Europe adopted its first EU climate law, under which more than 80 cities have signed the Clean Bus Declaration Act. The main goal is to ensure zero emissions by 2050, making Europe the first climate-neutral continent in the world. Numerous cities intend to purchase exclusively electric buses by 2025 (e.g., Athens, Paris) and others aim to achieve full electrification by 2030 (e.g., Oslo, Copenhagen) (Lu et al., 2023). Additionally, cities outside of Europe are in the process of replacing the conventional bus fleets with electric vehicles. Boston in the U.S. envisions achieving a fully zero-emission bus fleet by 2030 (He et al., 2023), Santiago, Chile and Bogotá, Colombia introduced the deployment of electric

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buses (McCabe and Ban, 2023), and in the U.K., the electric fleet is expected to triple its size by 2024. At last, in China, the electric buses constitute 60% of the public transport fleet (Wang et al., 2023). All these cases indicate the rapid expansion of electromobility in public transport, increasing the urgency of improving the tools for strategic and tactical planning.

Considering the layout of bus lines in the public transport network, the common practice for electric buses is to avoid making modifications to the existing bus lines. However, energy reserve limitations may occur, since the distances covered by electric buses may require greater energy than the capacity of e-buses (Perumal et al., 2022; Bie et al., 2021). As electric mobility becomes more entrenched in public transportation, vehicles with greater capacity and efficiency are developed and used by public transport operators. This offers the possibility to cover a large part of the transport network by electric buses without the need to charge. This also increases the quality of the service provided for passengers and can offer advantages in the scheduling of vehicles and crews. Nonetheless, the distances to be covered may be large, making it hard to overcome the demand for charging. One can consider that en-route charging might be a good solution, however, geographical, grid and operational cost limitations may arise (Zeng et al., 2022; Al-Saadi et al., 2022; Zeng et al., 2024). For instance, the formation of the area of bus stops may not allow the construction of en-route charging infrastructure. Another challenge may be the potential delays caused by charging during the route, which can negatively impact the quality of service. One potential solution is to increase the charging frequency of vehicles; however, this approach is likely to extend downtimes and necessitate the acquisition of additional electric buses, thereby raising both capital investment and operational costs (Liu et al., 2019).

When it comes to the tactical planning of electric bus networks, there is an imminent need for the resolution of problems like the vehicle scheduling problem, whose solution enables the efficient operation of the services. Initially, the scheduling for the electric buses is being made based on the corresponding charging infrastructure. Different types of charging methods affect the configuration of the schedule. For example, multiple charging outlets and stations, increasing the number of buses available for service, making it possible to improve the frequency of bus lines (Chau et al., 2024; Behnia et al., 2024). En-route charging can diminish the time out of service for electric buses (Zeng et al., 2022), offering greater possibilities and freedoms in the configuration of the schedule. Even so, there are other factors besides the charging infrastructure that need to be taken into consideration, such as the shifts of the drivers and the frequency and timetable demands that the passengers may have. In order to have efficient operations, all these matters should be taken into account.

Tackling all these obstacles is not an easy task for transport operators, as they have many decisions to make. For instance, the optimal planning of the bus network so that it covers large parts of the cities, the location of charging stations, and the charging method that best fits the features of the electric bus fleet. In addition, aspects such as the geography of the network and the availability of space for the installation of chargers are crucial to the operators' resolution.

Public transport is a service provided for civilians so they can commute to their destinations in a quick and efficient way. As a result, public transport operators who aim to implement electric buses in their fleet have to plan their operations considering also the quality of the service they offer. This means that the frequency, the timetables of bus lines, and the layout of the network should remain largely unchanged. These factors affect decisions like the location of charging stations, the method of charging, the bus routes of the bus lines, the number of required vehicles, and the vehicle and crew scheduling.

Given this discussion, the objective of this study is to address two problems arising from the transition to electric buses under a unified framework. The first problem concerns the necessary line modifications that may result from the introduction of electric bus fleets with limited autonomy, while the second is a vehicle scheduling problem in which electric buses are assigned to the trips of the lines. In particular, in conceptualizing the unified framework, we consider passenger demand at each bus stop on the examined lines, the deadheading time between the final stop of a trip and the depot, and the delay time associated with bus charging.

To address these two problems, a two-stage approach is employed. In the first stage, we introduce various bus line modification scenarios based on stop elimination options, as provided by the public transport operator. The first option is the existing layout of the line, when none of the stops are removed and the line length is unchanged. The second option modifies the line by removing a specific number of stops, which can be any number that is provided by the public transport authority based on their field knowledge and experience. The rest of the options can eliminate more or less stops compared to the second option (e.g. increasing or decreasing number of removed stops by one at a time). After these planning options are defined, a line planning modification scenario emerges for each option. For each scenario and respective line layout, the electric bus scheduling is created, while accounting for the charging requirements of the fleet. To achieve this, we reformulate the Vehicle Scheduling Problem (VSP) for electric buses, incorporating the timetables and trips of all examined lines, bus autonomy, trip distances, and deadheading distances. The proposed formulation of the E-VSP calculates the minimum number of electric buses needed to support the trip services of the modified lines, thereby introducing operational costs as well. In the second stage, we select the optimal modification scenario for each bus line considered by solving a second mathematical programming model. The goal of this second stage and the respective model is to examine several candidate line modification scenarios (i.e., candidate solutions of the model) and their trade-offs, to select the optimal one that minimizes unserved passenger demand.

By applying this modeling approach, this study contributes to the efficient planning of bus lines and the scheduling of vehicles for electric bus fleets in public transport systems. The findings can provide useful insights for transportation authorities and transport operators wishing to optimize the layout of bus lines and the scheduling for electric buses, thus contributing to the reduction of emissions and the shaping of a sustainable urban environment.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a detailed review of related literature. Section 3 presents the mathematical formulation of our model, including the specific constraints and objectives considered. Section 4 presents experimental results on our case studies and a sensitivity analysis. Finally, in the concluding remarks section, the paper summarizes the findings and discusses potential future research directions.

2. Literature review

This section reviews studies on bus line planning and modification, as well as vehicle scheduling for both conventional and electric fleets. It concludes by highlighting the knowledge gap that the present study seeks to address.

2.1. Line planning problem

The line planning problem (LPP) is considered to be a fundamental problem in the field of strategic planning of public transport services, and often considered as a part of the Transit Network Design Problem (TNDP). The LPP is typically presented as a single, combined task that includes planning the network lines and the frequencies of the respective services (but not the scheduling of the vehicles). Over the years, several approaches and mathematical formulations have been proposed, considering conventional bus fleets. In recent years, due to the shift to electric mobility in public transport, some studies have taken into account the changes needed in the transport network to satisfy the needs of electric fleets. These changes may affect the planning of a bus route, the layout of the line, the passengers' demand, and the frequency of the trips of a bus line.

Among the early approaches to the LPP for conventional fleets, [Borndörfer et al. \(2008\)](#) presented two new multi-commodity flow models, which compute optimal line routes and passengers' paths. The two models were integer linear programs. In addition, an in-depth analysis of past studies related to basic line planning models can be found in the seminal work of [Schöbel \(2012\)](#). In the work of [Lyu et al. \(2019\)](#), a Multinomial Logit model (MNL) was developed that investigates the probability of a passenger choosing a Custom Bus service over a set of alternative modes such as traditional bus, metro, and taxi. The purpose of this study was to plan bus lines that can balance service quality with profit by developing a heuristic solution framework that includes a grid-density-based clustering method for discovering potential travel demands. [Chen et al. \(2021\)](#) also propose a mathematical formulation for customized bus routes for passengers with similar demands when traveling from home to work. To this purpose, they develop a multi-objective optimization problem, where a constructive two-stage heuristic algorithm is applied to generate a Pareto solution in a real-world multimodal travel corridor with actual travel demands in Beijing.

Several studies have considered altering existing bus lines in order to better serve the transport network. For example, [Avila-Ordóñez et al. \(2022\)](#) introduce a method where some of the existing lines are replaced with alternative lines in the case of announced events. Adaptations are made only to a subset of lines, ensuring that changes minimize inconvenience for passengers and improve total travel time. To implement this, they develop heuristic algorithms, based on genetic algorithms, which automatically design these alternative lines in a three-step process. As the adoption of electromobility has increased in recent years, many studies focus on the changes that will occur in the public transport networks. In a survey paper, [Perumal et al. \(2022\)](#) reviewed past studies related to electromobility and gave an overview of the different aspects in the planning process of electric vehicles on a strategic, tactical and operational level. [Barraza and Estrada \(2021\)](#) developed a MILP model using grid enumeration at the objective function, aiming to minimize the total costs. Their bus network design problem minimized the total cost of the system, composed of the infrastructure and the operating cost, the emission cost, and the time cost. [Jiang and Zhang \(2019\)](#) investigate electric bus route planning, focusing on the optimization of operational parameters for bus lines as well as the strategic placement and setup of charging stations and charging infrastructure. To implement this, a social welfare maximization model is established, where a heuristic solution algorithm is proposed based on Lagrangian method.

Furthermore, [Su et al. \(2023\)](#) investigate the design problem of an electric bus route with charging stations to smooth the operations between e-bus service and charging. A mathematical programming model is proposed to maximize social welfare in consideration of the uncertain charging demand at charging stations. The developed algorithm was designed to optimize the problem variables, such as the number of stops, fares, service headway, fleet size, and charging piles. Lastly, [Zhang et al. \(2021\)](#) develop a bi-level programming framework to formulate the electric transit route network design problem. In the upper level of the model, they determine the route structure and charging station location, aiming to optimize the total costs of both user and operator. The lower-level passenger assignment model aims to calculate the user cost for the upper-level model. The model is solved by a genetic algorithm (GA), which can search all possible route structures through designed genetic operators.

2.2. Electric vehicle scheduling problem

Considering the vehicle scheduling stage of our problem, we have conducted an in depth review of the relevant literature. We note that the VSP is a well-known NP-hard problem ([Bertossi et al., 1987](#); [Bish et al., 2001](#); [Bunte and Kliewer, 2009](#); [Gharibi et al., 2020](#)). Thus, the E-VSP is an NP-hard problem as well because it is reducible in polynomial time to the VSP problem. The VSP can take different forms and variations, depending on the formulation of the problem. Due to the shift from conventional fuels to electric energy in public transport, new needs emerge in the tactical planning of the network. Thus, studies are investigating the modification of the VSP model in order to adjust to electric vehicles, creating the Electric Vehicle Scheduling Problem (E-VSP). A comprehensive analysis and review of relevant studies related to the timetabling and vehicle scheduling problem can be found in the survey paper of [Alamatsaz et al. \(2022\)](#), which lists heuristic and exact solution approaches.

One early approach to this problem, provided by [Chao and Xiaohong \(2013\)](#), proposed a modification of the existing VSP model for the single depot vehicle scheduling problem, with route time constraints. The model of this study was a multi-objective MILP problem solved with the NSGA-II algorithm. It consists of two independent objective functions applied in the scheduling model, one minimizing the investment cost for the electric fleet and the other minimizing the total charging demand in stations. [Häll et al. \(2019\)](#) are investigating how the electric buses are going to affect the operations of a public transit system, both in the design of the route

network and in the timetabling and vehicle scheduling process. They suggest that alterations should be made in the line planning process, considering the location of the bus stops and depots, especially when the vehicles require overnight charging. They mention that charging locations and different charging techniques may affect the planning process in different aspects, such as the layout of the lines, routing, scheduling, passenger demand, and level of service. All these aspects affect the line planning process as well as the vehicle scheduling procedure for electric buses. For this purpose, they introduce a mathematical problem for the scheduling of electric vehicles. The objective function is to minimize the number of buses used as well as minimize the deadheading distance. Similarly, [Teng et al. \(2020\)](#) developed an integrated multi-objective model for the VSP for electric buses, for a single bus line. The objectives concern the smoothing of the vehicle departure intervals (timetabling), the minimizing of the required number of vehicles and total charging costs.

[Gkiotsalitis et al. \(2023\)](#) introduced an exact approach on the multi-depot electric vehicle scheduling problem, considering time windows in which vehicles can recharge at charging stations located at any point of the service operation area (EB-MDVSP_{TW}). The formulation considers the operational cost of vehicles and the waiting times. Furthermore, it examines the capacity of charging stations and does not allow the simultaneous charging of different vehicles at the same charger. The objective of this model is to minimize the waiting time cost, and it was solved with global optimality using the branch-and-cut method. Some other studies combine optimization models with heuristic methods. For example, [Yao et al. \(2020\)](#) develop an optimization model called MVT-E-VSP, a VSP model for multiple vehicle types, including electric buses, which is solved based on a heuristic algorithm. The heuristic methodology is developed to solve the MVT-E-VSP combining an algorithm to obtain schedules for EBs and a GA to find the optimal solution. The goal is to minimize the total investment cost, and the method was implemented in the Daxing District, Beijing. Similarly, [Wu et al. \(2022\)](#) introduced a bi-objective multi-depot electric vehicle scheduling problem (MDVSP). The objectives were to minimize the total operation cost and to minimize the peak load resulting from recharging activities. To this end, a time-expanded network is produced, using a branch-and-price method, which is embedded with a heuristic algorithm and a trip chain pool strategy. The results were verified through a real-world network in Guangzhou, China. Furthermore, [Liu et al. \(2022\)](#) proposed a meta-heuristic approach with a two-stage solution method for an electric vehicle scheduling problem. In the first step, a simulated annealing algorithm (SA) is used to generate a set of possible solutions, while in the second step, a local search (LS) is combined with a departure-time adjustment procedure (DTAP) to fabricate the final scheduling solution. Lastly, [Yıldırım and Yıldız \(2021\)](#) introduce a binary integer programming model aimed at minimizing both bus procurement and operational costs. To efficiently solve large-scale instances, a column generation (CG) method is employed, powered by a novel dynamic programming algorithm designed to solve a generalized resource-constrained shortest path problem during each iteration.

2.3. Study contribution

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the Combined Line Planning Modification and Electric Vehicle Scheduling Problem has not yet been formally introduced and addressed in the literature. Nonetheless, a number of mathematical programming models addressing either line planning (or its modification) or electric vehicle scheduling have been proposed over the past years. These approaches differ with respect to their planning horizons, decision variables, and optimization objectives. [Table 1](#) highlights the contribution of the present study in relation to existing research streams on optimal electric vehicle scheduling and line planning.

As shown in [Table 1](#), several studies have examined line planning or modification problems as well as electric vehicle scheduling problems independently; however, their joint investigation within a single study has not yet been addressed in the literature. [Häll et al. \(2019\)](#) highlighted the need for reconfiguring the public network and bus line layout when it involves electric vehicles, but they did not present a corresponding model formulation. In this study, we attempt to combine these two problems by considering the charging needs of the vehicles, the demand for passenger transport and the number of available vehicles. All these factors are capable of affecting the network layout as well as the scheduling procedure. With the implementation of this study, and considering all these elements, we are trying to determine the optimal layout of the bus line, in combination with the best vehicle scheduling option, for a given number of vehicles. One can also notice that a few studies take into consideration the passengers' demand, as well as other limitations such as charging, time scheduling constraints, deadheading distances and fleet size. This study, on the other hand, formulates a model that takes into account all of these aspects. Moreover, our formulated model allocates trips to specific chargers and charging time slots, so there are no delays due to waiting time. Summarizing, our study's contributions are the following:

1. development of a combined mathematical model for the modification of lines and vehicle scheduling for electric vehicles and incorporation of limitations, such as charging and vehicle battery autonomy, to the model's formulation,
2. introduction of a two-stage solution method for the combined mathematical model,
3. provision of a trade-off solution that considers the operational costs of electric bus lines under resource constraints while addressing the transportation needs of passengers,
4. demonstration of the model application to two case studies in two different urban areas (Athens, Greece and Limassol, Cyprus),
5. sensitivity analysis of the solutions derived by our approach for the electric bus networks.

Methodologically, in the following section, we propose a mixed integer quadratic model (MIQP) that provides an electric vehicle scheduling tool, which takes into consideration deadheading distances from the last bus stop to the depots, the level of battery and autonomy of the vehicle and the timetable. This scheduling tool is applied in different options, which arise from the modification of the existing routes. Once the vehicle scheduling is completed, our MILP model for modification of lines, which considers the passengers' demand in each bus stop, selects the optimal modification-option of the bus routes for all the examined lines, depending on the available fleet. As mentioned before, the E-VSP is an NP-hard problem which is computationally intractable for large problem

Table 1
Literature review summary.

Reference	Optimization goal	Solution approach	Line Planning	E-VSP	Charging Location	Fleet Size Consideration	Deadheading Distances	Passenger Demand	Modification of Line
Borndörfer et al. (2008)	traveling time, TCO	MILP	✓					✓	✓
Lyu et al. (2019)	bus stop locations, routes, timetables, walking distance, profit	MNL, heuristic	✓					✓	✓
Jiang and Zhang (2019)	travel time, passengers' service, line layout	heuristic						✓	✓
Zhang et al. (2021)	operating cost, passengers' cost	MINLP, GA	✓					✓	
Chen et al. (2021)	operating cost, passengers' profit	heuristic						✓	✓
Barraza and Estrada (2021)	agency cost, emissions and travel time	MILP	✓		charging stations		✓	✓	✓
Avila-Ordóñez et al. (2022)	travel time, passengers' welfare	heuristic						✓	✓
Su et al. (2023)	social welfare	heuristic	✓					✓	
Chao and Xiaohong (2013)	capital investment and charging demand	MILP, NSGA- II		✓	charging stations	✓	✓		
Häll et al. (2019)	Number of used buses and deadheading trips	MILP		✓	charging stations		✓		
Teng et al. (2020)	vehicle departure intervals, number of vehicles and charging costs	MOPSO		✓	depot	✓	✓	✓	
Yao et al. (2020)	scheduling costs, purchasing costs, operating costs of deadheading and timetabled trips	MILP, heuristic		✓	depot		✓	✓	
Yildirim and Yildiz (2021)	procurement cost, operational cost	MILP		✓	depot	✓	✓		
Wu et al. (2022)	operation cost and peak load from recharging	MILP, heuristic		✓	charging stations	✓	✓		
Liu et al. (2022)	operation cost, service quality	meta-heuristic		✓	charging stations	✓		✓	
Gkiotsalitis et al. (2023)	waiting cost	MILP		✓	depot	✓	✓		
This study	number of vehicles, passengers' demand	MIQP, MILP, heuristic	✓	✓	depot	✓	✓	✓	✓

instances. To rectify this, we employ a time-slice heuristic in order to generate sub-problems with fewer decision variables that can be solved with less computation time. The results from this step (the calculated number of vehicles) are fed to the line planning modification tool. This tool, with the best scheduling solution that arises from the E-VSP model, offers a globally optimal solution regarding the layout of the examined lines. The mathematical formulation for this is presented below.

3. Formulation of the combined line planning modification and vehicle scheduling problem for a fleet of electric buses

In this study, the problem is formulated according to a two-stage process, firstly formulating the E-VSP (Section 3.1) as a MIQP model, and then, on a second stage, formulating the line planning modification problem as a MILP model (Section 3.3).

In the first stage, the solution to the E-VSP provides an optimized scheduling for electric buses for all the different modifications of the bus routes examined, when taking into account deadhead distances, real-world timetables, as well as electric bus consumption and battery capacity. All the essential parameters, such as frequencies, number of itineraries, etc. are provided by the transport operator for the examined lines. When applying the E-VSP to the modifications, these parameters remain the same for all the options. That means that the examined alterations of the bus line layouts maintain the same frequencies, number of routes, and the rest of the parameters of the scheduling problem as defined in the following sub-sections. In the second stage, based on the results of the E-VSP, a solution to the line planning modification model is derived, which can be used for the optimal re-planning of existing bus lines, when considering the bus autonomy and the passengers' demand, for a specific fleet size.

3.1. Mathematical formulation for the E-VSP

The problem concerning the electric vehicle scheduling model (E-VSP) is described as follows:

"Given a specific timetable for each bus line and a pool of \mathcal{K} electric vehicles, performing a number of tasks \mathcal{N} , map each bus to tasks \mathcal{N} so that it satisfies the time limitations given by the timetable and the demand of vehicles for charging, while having as a goal the minimization of vehicles required for operating the line."

The main assumptions of the problem are the following:

1. Each line is associated with a specific charging location, which is located at the corresponding depot of the line.
2. The time needed to recharge after a trip varies depending on the vehicle's remaining battery level.
3. Vehicles leave charging stations after being recharged up to their maximum allowed battery level, which is 350 kW-hours (kWh). Their energy level when operating itineraries should not be less than 20% of the maximum capacity, otherwise the completion of routes might be at risk.
4. A charging time slot is fully occupied by a vehicle, regardless of the actual charging duration of the vehicle. That is, the corresponding charger is considered occupied for the entire duration of the time slot, even if the bus has finished its charging before the end of the slot. This way of organizing the charging procedure ensures that there is no waiting time for the charging of the vehicles.
5. Vehicles can head to charging after reaching their final stop per line direction.
6. The timetables for trips are planned in advance by public transport operators, and the timetables for charging are organized through the charging time-slot system mentioned above.

In this problem definition, we consider all the activities that need to be performed by vehicles as nodes in a graph. Firstly, we have a pre-defined number of trips \mathcal{V} according to the timetable of each line. Secondly, we consider a set \mathcal{F} , which represents all of the possible charging events at the depot. Each possible charging event $i \in \mathcal{F}$ can start within the time window $[a, b]$. In this time window, a is considered as the time point where bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ has performed trip $i \in \mathcal{V}$ and has traveled from the final bus stop to the charging destination, and b is the time point after the mentioned travel time, plus the time needed to complete the charging procedure. In addition, we consider two sets \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{D} , representing the depot and the last stop on each line. Evidently, all the tasks that a bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ can perform belong to the set \mathcal{N} , where $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{D}$ and $\mathcal{V} \cap \mathcal{F} \cap \mathcal{O} \cap \mathcal{D} = \emptyset$.

The set of potentially required buses $k \in \mathcal{K}$ to perform tasks $i \in \mathcal{N}$ consists of two sub-sets: \mathcal{K}_1 and \mathcal{K}_2 . While set \mathcal{K}_1 represents the vehicles that did not perform any tasks $i \in \mathcal{N}$ in a specific time-slice, set \mathcal{K}_2 includes the vehicles that did. This separation of set $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is necessary because, in the formulation of the E-VSP, we divide the operating hours of each line into parts consisting of time-slices. Therefore, it becomes crucial to keep track of the required buses per slice. The E-VSP is solved in each time-slice with the use of the MIQP model. Using a heuristic approach, we assign buses to sets $\mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2$, and we also succeed in transferring the time and battery level state of a bus from one slice to another. The reason behind using a heuristic and solving the E-VSP in slices is that the E-VSP is an NP-hard problem. With this approach and formulation, we manage to solve the problem without computational limitations, finding the best solution per time-slice and a comprehensive solution for the entire operating day of a line.

Considering the parameters of the problem, the duration of a task $i \in \mathcal{N}$ that a bus k performs is τ'_i . In addition, the travel time between the end location of task $i \in \mathcal{N}$ and the start location of task $j \in \mathcal{N}$ is τ_{ij} . The energy consumption caused by the distance covered between the locations of nodes (i, j) is θ_{ij} , and the distance covered is d_{ij} .

The battery consumption per traveled distance is e and the charging rate is c . In addition, the minimum allowed state of charge of a bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is SOC_{\min} and the maximum allowed state of charge is SOC_{\max} . In order to successfully transfer the data regarding the location, battery level and time of each bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ performing task $i \in \mathcal{N}$ from one time-slice to another, we have established some parameters. The state of charge for the buses at the beginning of a time-slice is E_k , the location of the bus (either the first or final stop of the line or the depot) is L_k , and the time that each bus k is available in each time-slice is $Time_k$.

The decision variables of the problem include:

- $x_{ijk} \in \{0, 1\}$, where $x_{ijk} = 1$ if bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ uses arc $(i, j) \in \mathcal{N}$ and 0 otherwise.
- $y_k \in \{0, 1\}$, where $y_k = 1$ if bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is used in any time slice and 0 otherwise.

The notation of this problem is summarized in Table 2.

In Fig. 1, a generic graphical representation of the modeled problem is provided. The $o_k \in \mathcal{O}$ is the origin point, consisting of two nodes. The first node is the depot, and the second node is the last bus stop of every trip for every bus line examined. The d_k is the destination point, which consists of the last two nodes of the model. These two last nodes also represent the depot and the last bus stop, respectively. This formulation helps us keep track of the location of bus k when transferring the data concerning the location, energy and time status of the bus, from one time-slice to another. For example, if a bus k is located at the final stop of its route at the end of the time slice, then, consequently, at the next time-slice, it is located at the second node of the origin point o_k . Nonetheless, all buses have to complete their whole trip at the end of a time-slice, meaning they are either located at the last stop of their route or they managed to transfer to their corresponding depot.

As previously discussed, each bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ transfers from the origin point to its first bus stop, in order to serve the trip that it is assigned to. Considering the limitations regarding the battery level, some of the buses in each time slice are also heading for charging. Each charging event is represented by a node. After the completion of charging, the vehicle continues with its trip tasks and, eventually, goes to the destination point d_k (final stop of its route or depot). It should be clarified that the charging stations are located at the corresponding depot of each examined line. This process is depicted in Fig. 2.

Table 2
Nomenclature of the E-VSP problem.

Sets	
\mathcal{V}	set of number of trips according to the timetable of each line (inner tasks).
\mathcal{F}	set of charging events.
\mathcal{O}	set of starting node.
\mathcal{D}	set of ending node.
\mathcal{N}	set of all possible tasks, where $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$ and $\mathcal{V} \cap \mathcal{F} \cap \mathcal{O} \cap \mathcal{D} = \emptyset$.
\mathcal{K}	set of all vehicles.
\mathcal{K}_1	set of all vehicles not used in a time-slice.
\mathcal{K}_2	set of all vehicles used in a time-slice.
Parameters	
SOC_{\min}	minimum allowed state of charge for every vehicle k .
SOC_{\max}	maximum allowed state of charge for every vehicle k .
e	energy consumption per meter.
c	charging rate per minute.
t'_i	duration of task $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
t_{ij}	elapsed time on arc (i, j) , which is equal to the travel time between the end location of task $i \in \mathcal{N}$ and the start location of task $j \in \mathcal{N}$.
θ_{ij}	energy consumption when traveling between the locations of nodes i and j .
d_{ij}	distance between the end location of node i and the start location of node j .
dt_j	departure time of every trip (task) $j \in \mathcal{V}$.
o_k	the source node associated with the depot housing vehicle k .
d_k	the sink node associated with the depot housing vehicle k .
b_k	a binary vector, that indicates if a vehicle k is used in any of the time slices. It takes the value 0 if a bus is used and 1 otherwise.
E_k	the state of charge for the buses at the beginning of any time slice.
$Time_k$	the time that each vehicle k used in any time slice starts its service.
L_k	the location of each bus at the beginning of the time slice. This is either the starting stop of the bus line or the terminal stop.
M	a sufficiently large positive number.
B	the number of available buses.
Decision Variables	
x_{ijk}	binary variables, where $x_{ijk} = 1$ if vehicle k traverses arc (i, j) and 0 otherwise.
y_k	binary variables that take the value 1 if bus $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is used in any time slice and 0 otherwise.
Variables	
σ_{ijk}	continuous variables, where $\sigma_{ijk} = 0$ if there is a connection between (i, j) and $\sigma_{ijk} \in [-M, M]$ if not, where M is a big positive number.
T_{ik}	time that service begins at node $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
SOC_{ik}^s	continuous variables, indicating the state of charge of the vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at the start of the task $i \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$.
SOC_{ik}^e	continuous variables, indicating the state of charge of the vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}$ at the end of the task $i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$.
g_{ik}	continuous variables, indicating the change in the state of charge of the vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}$ when performing task $i \in \mathcal{N}$. A positive value of variable g_{ik} indicates energy consumption, whereas a negative value indicates the energy gained from the charging procedure.
τ_{ik}	continuous variables, indicating the required time period to recharge vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}$ via charging event $i \in \mathcal{F}$.

The formulation presented is being solved in each time slice with a mixed-integer quadratic programming model, giving us the best solution for each time slice. That is, the minimum buses required for the service of the trips in each time slice. This result comes considering the deadhead distance, the timetable and charging limitations. The mathematical model for the E-VSP is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\min \quad & \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{j \in (\mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D})} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} x_{ijk} \\
& + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} b_k y_k \\
& + p_1 \sum_{i \in (\mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V})} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} T_{jk} x_{ijk} \\
& + p_2 \sum_{i \in (\mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V})} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} t_{ij} x_{ijk} \\
& - p_3 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} SOC_{ik}^s
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

s.t.:

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} x_{o_k j k} \leq 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_1 \tag{2}$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} x_{o_k j k} = 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_1 \tag{3}$$

MODELED NETWORK REPRESENTATION

Fig. 1. A generic representation of the modeled problem.

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} x_{o_k j k} \leq 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_2 \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} x_{o_k j k} = 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_2 \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{O}} x_{i j k} = 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (6)$$

$$x_{i j k} = 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}, \forall j \in \mathcal{O}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{i j k} \leq 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{D}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (8)$$

$$x_{i j k} = 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{D}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i j k} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}} x_{i j k} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (10)$$

$$x_{i j k} = 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{F}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} x_{i j k} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} x_{j i k} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} x_{i j k} \leq 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{i j k} = 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{V} \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} x_{i j k} \leq B \quad (15)$$

$$x_{i j k} = 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall j \in \mathcal{N} : i = j \quad (16)$$

$$T_{j k} \leq M(1 - x_{i j k}) + dt_j \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (17)$$

$$T_{j k} \geq -M(1 - x_{i j k}) + dt_j \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (18)$$

$$T_{j k} \leq M \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{i j k} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (19)$$

Fig. 2. A generic representation of the time-slice modeling approach. Each time slice solves the E-VSP problem based on the location, energy level and time status of a vehicle k provided by the previous time-slice. In the case of the first time slice, the location of vehicle k at the beginning of the time slice is the depot and the energy level is SOC_{max} .

$$(T_{ik} + t'_i + t_{ij})x_{ijk} - T_{jk}x_{ijk} \leq 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (20)$$

$$(T_{ik} + (SOC_{ik}^e - SOC_{ik}^s)/c + t_{ij})x_{ijk} - T_{jk}x_{ijk} \leq 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{F}, \forall j \in \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (21)$$

$$T_{ik} \leq Time_k + M(1 - x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (22)$$

$$T_{ik} \geq Time_k - M(1 - x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (23)$$

$$T_{jk} \leq T_{ik} + t'_i + t_{ij} + M(1 - x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{D} \quad (24)$$

$$T_{jk} \geq T_{ik} + t'_i + t_{ij} - M(1 - x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{D} \quad (25)$$

$$T_{jk} \leq T_{ik} + (SOC_{ik}^e - SOC_{ik}^s)/c + t_{ij} + M(1 - x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{F}, \forall j \in \mathcal{D} \quad (26)$$

$$T_{jk} \geq T_{ik} + (SOC_{ik}^e - SOC_{ik}^s)/c + t_{ij} - M(1 - x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{F}, \forall j \in \mathcal{D} \quad (27)$$

$$SOC_{jk}^s \geq SOC_{min} - M(1 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{D} \quad (28)$$

$$SOC_{jk}^s \leq M \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (29)$$

$$SOC_{ik}^e \leq E_k + M(1 - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \quad (30)$$

$$SOC_{ik}^e \geq E_k - M(1 - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \quad (31)$$

$$SOC_{ik}^e \leq M \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} x_{ijk} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (32)$$

$$SOC_{jk}^s \leq SOC_{ik}^e - \theta_{ij} + M(1 - \sum x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (33)$$

$$SOC_{jk}^s \geq SOC_{ik}^e - \theta_{ij} - M(1 - \sum x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (34)$$

$$g_{jk} \leq SOC_{jk}^s - SOC_{jk}^e + M(1 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (35)$$

$$g_{jk} \geq SOC_{jk}^s - SOC_{jk}^e - M(1 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (36)$$

$$g_{jk} \leq e_j + M(1 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{V} \quad (37)$$

$$g_{jk} \geq e_j - M(1 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{V} \quad (38)$$

$$g_{jk} \leq SOC_{jk}^s - SOC_{max} + M(1 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \quad (39)$$

$$g_{jk} \geq SOC_{jk}^s - SOC_{max} - M(1 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{V}} x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \quad (40)$$

$$g_{jk} \leq M \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} x_{ijk} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (41)$$

$$g_{jk} \geq -M \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} x_{ijk} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \quad (42)$$

$$y_k M \geq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} x_{ijk} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (43)$$

$$y_k \leq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} x_{ijk} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (44)$$

Objective function (1) is used to minimize the number of vehicles required to cover the scheduled trips. In more detail, $\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{j \in (\mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D})} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} x_{ijk}$ minimizes the connections between tasks $i, j \in \mathcal{N}$. The term $\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \beta_k y_k$ minimizes the number of buses used at the current time-slice. The variable y_k takes the value of 1 if a vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}$ is used in a time-slice, or zero otherwise. Parameter b_k takes values 0–1 accordingly, in each time-slice, through a heuristic. Therefore, this summation takes the minimum value when the minimum number of vehicles is used per time-slice. The other two terms of the objective function $p_1 \sum_{i \in (\mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V})} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} T_{jk} x_{ijk}$, $p_2 \sum_{i \in (\mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V})} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} t_{ij} x_{ijk}$, aim to assign vehicles k in arcs $i, j \in \mathcal{N}$, so that vehicle k performs the earliest possible task in each time-slice and makes the nearest connection between two nodes, therefore wasting the minimum time needed, t_{ij} . Finally, the term $-p_3 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} SOC_{ik}^s$, strives to make each vehicle k start with as high as possible energy level in each time-slice. These three terms also contribute to the reduction of vehicles required for the daily operation of an examined line. Furthermore, it should be clarified that p_1, p_2, p_3 are penalty parameters, which are applied to the respective terms in order to reduce the priority of the last three terms of the objective function in comparison with the first two terms.

Constraints (2) and (4) ensure that each vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2$, leaves from the starting point o_k at most once to perform any task $j \in \mathcal{N}$. Equality constraints (3) and (5) ensure that a vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2$ does not visit the starting point o_k after performing tasks $j \in \mathcal{N}$. Constraints (6) prohibit vehicle k from connecting tasks i, j , when i, j both belong to the starting point. Additionally, constraint (7) forbids vehicle k to visit the starting point o_k , after charging events, trips or arriving at a destination point, and (9) forbids vehicle k from performing any activity after visiting the destination point. Constraints (8) ensure that each vehicle k reaches the destination point d_k at most once, after performing task $i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$. Constraints (10) ensure that every vehicle k that leaves the starting point o_k to perform any task $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$ must also reach the destination point d_k . Constraints (11) indicate that a vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}$ cannot visit a charging node $j \in \mathcal{F}$, after already having visited a charging node $i \in \mathcal{F}$. Constraints (12) are flow conservation constraints ensuring that every vehicle k which enters a node $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$ should also leave this node towards any node $i \in \mathcal{N}$. Constraints (13) indicate that every node $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$ is visited at most once by any vehicle k from any node $i \in \mathcal{N}$. Constraints (14) ensure that every inner task $j \in \mathcal{V}$ is being performed from a vehicle k , after visiting any node $i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$. Constraints (15) make sure that the number of vehicles k leaving the starting point o_k to perform tasks $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$ is less than or equal to the number of available vehicles. Lastly, constraints (16) guarantee that a vehicle k does not perform self-visits in any of the nodes $i \in \mathcal{N}, j \in \mathcal{N}$.

Eqs. (17) to (25) are the time flow constraints, which regulate the vehicle scheduling problem according to the given timetable and time needed to cover the distances between the nodes $i, j \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$.

The combined application of constraints (17) and (18) ensures that if a vehicle k uses arc $(i, j), i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$, then the time variable T_{jk} , indicating the starting time of vehicle k performing task $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$ is equal to the departure time dt_j of trip $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$. Constraints (19) indicate that the variable T_{jk} can take a value only if vehicle k uses arc $(i, j), i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$. Constraints (20), indicate that if a vehicle k uses arc $(i, j), i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$, then variable T_{jk} can take the value of variable T_{ik} plus the time required to perform task i and the elapsed time from task i to j , only if k uses arc (i, j) . Similarly, for Eq. (21) variable T_{jk} can take the value of variable T_{ik} plus the time required for recharging at charging node $i \in \mathcal{F}$ and the elapsed time from task i to j , only if k uses arc (i, j) . One can notice that a nonlinearity arises from the fact that variables $T_{jk}, T_{ik}, SOC_{ik}^e, SOC_{ik}^s$ are multiplied by variables x_{ijk} . In Section 3.2 we showcase how constraints (20) and (21) are linearized. Constraints (22) and (23) ensure that if a vehicle k uses arc $(o_k, j), j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$, the starting time of the starting node task is equal to the values of parameter $Time_k$, indicating the instant that a vehicle k starts the service at any time-slice. Constraints (24) and (25) make sure that if a vehicle k uses arc (i, d_k) , the starting time of the ending node is equal to the starting time of task $i \in \mathcal{V}$, plus the travel time between the location of task i and the ending node d_k and the duration of task i . Constraints (26) and (27), indicate that the arrival time T_{i, d_k} at ending node d_k after visiting charging node $i \in \mathcal{F}$ is equal to the starting time of task i , the time required for vehicle k to recharge and the traveling time between nodes i and d_k .

Constraints (28) to (44) are the energy flow constraints, which regulate the vehicle scheduling problem according to the energy demands of the vehicles and the battery autonomy. Alongside the time flow constraints and nodes modeling constraints, they formulate the vehicle scheduling model for electric buses.

Constraints (28) ensure that if a vehicle $k \in \mathcal{K}$ uses arc (i, j) , then the state of charge at the start of task node $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$ is greater than or equal to the minimum allowed state of charge SOC_{min} . Constraints (29), (32) make sure that only if a vehicle k uses arc (i, j) the variables SOC_{jk}^s, SOC_{jk}^e can take their appropriate values. Otherwise, $SOC_{jk}^s = 0$ and $SOC_{jk}^e = 0$. Constraints (30) and (31) make certain that if a vehicle k is leaving the starting node o_k to perform any task $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$, then the state of charge at the starting node is equal to the parameter E_k , indicating the state of energy of vehicle k at the beginning of any time slice. Constraints (33) and (34) ensure that if a vehicle k uses arc (i, j) , the state of charge at the start of task $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$ is equal to the state of charge at the end of task $i \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$, minus the energy consumption caused by the distance covered between the locations of nodes

(i, j). Constraints (35) and (36) ensure that if node $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$ is visited by vehicle k , then the difference between the state of charge at the start of task j , SOC_{jk}^s and the state of charge of vehicle k at the end of task j , SOC_{jk}^e is equal to g_{jk} . Constraints (37) and (38) ensure that if a vehicle k uses arc (i, j) , then g_{jk} is equal to the energy consumption caused by performing task $j \in \mathcal{V}$. Constraints (39), (40) make certain that if a vehicle k reaches charging node $j \in \mathcal{F}$, then g_{jk} takes the value of the amount of energy gained by the charging procedure, which is $SOC_{jk}^s - SOC_{max}$. The energy gained is modeled as a negative value. Constraints (41) and (42) ensure that if node $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$ is not visited, then $g_{jk} = 0$. Lastly, (43) and (44) ensure that variable y_k , which indicates if a vehicle k is used in any time slice or not, takes a value if vehicle k traverses an arc (i, j) , otherwise $y_k = 0$.

3.2. Reformulation as a mixed-integer quadratic program

One may notice that the mathematical formulation of the constraints of the E-VSP problem, as shared in sub-Section 3.1, is nonlinear. Specifically, constraints (20) and (21), which express the time continuity of our model, are nonlinear because variables T_{jk} , T_{ik} , SOC_{ik}^e , SOC_{ik}^s are multiplied by variables x_{ijk} . To reformulate these constraints as linear ones, we introduce variables σ_{ijk} , which are used to reformulate constraints (20) and (21) into constraints (45) to (46):

$$T_{ik} + t'_i + t_{ij} - T_{jk} + \sigma_{ijk} \leq 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (45)$$

$$T_{ik} + (SOC_{ik}^e - SOC_{ik}^s)/c + t_{ij} - T_{jk} + \sigma_{ijk} \leq 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{F}, \forall j \in \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (46)$$

Similarly to constraints (20) to (21), constraints (45) and (46) need to guarantee that if a vehicle k uses arc (i, j) for $i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}$, $j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D}$, then variable T_{jk} can take the value of variable T_{ik} plus the time required to perform task i and the elapsed time from task i to j , only if k uses arc (i, j) . Likewise, in constraint (46), variable T_{jk} can take the value of variable T_{ik} plus the time required for recharging at charging node $i \in \mathcal{F}$ and the elapsed time from task i to j , only if k uses arc (i, j) .

To achieve that modeling for constraints (45) and (46), we need to further include constraints (47) and (48) that allow σ_{ijk} to take values according to whether x_{ijk} is equal to 0 or 1.

$$\sigma_{ijk} \leq M(1 - x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (47)$$

$$\sigma_{ijk} \geq -M(1 - x_{ijk}) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{D} \quad (48)$$

Constraints (45), (46) work together with (47), (48), and are equisatisfiable with constraints (20) and (21). In more detail, if $x_{ijk} = 0$, then variable σ_{ijk} , is relaxed to take any value in $[-M, M]$. In turn, inequalities (45), (46) are relaxed since the variables involved can take any value in their respective definition space.

On the other hand, if $x_{ijk} = 1$, then variables σ_{ijk} for specific combinations of i, j, k are forced to take the value of zero. This would mean that the corresponding inequalities (45) and (46) need to hold for the rest of the variables involved ($T_{ik}, t'_i, t_{ij}, T_{jk}$). In this way, in Eq. (45), T_{jk} , which models the time that task j start its activity, can take the value of variable T_{ik} (time that task i starts its activity) plus the time required to perform task i and the elapsed time from task i to j . The same logic applies to constraint (46). By introducing variables σ_{ijk} , the multiplication of variables x_{ijk} , SOC_{ik}^e , SOC_{ik}^s and T_{jk} is not needed in the equation, resulting in a linear constraint with the form of inequality (46).

Given these reformulations, all constraints of the E-VSP are now linear, resulting in a MIQP formulation of the problem. The reformulated constraints of the MIQP form a polyhedron, resulting in a feasible region which is a convex set.

3.3. Mathematical formulation for the line planning modification model

The problem concerning the line planning modification model works together with the model of the electric vehicle scheduling problem (E-VSP). For every line modification scenario of an examined bus line, the E-VSP model presented in the previous sub-section is applied. As mentioned above, several modifications options can be examined by the proposed methodology and the E-VSP for the bus line network under study. These modifications options arise from the elimination of a different number of bus stops for each line. While our methodology is robust and any number of stops can be selected/removed for a scenario (given that they exist), in our application, the first option is the existing layout of the examined line, without any changes. The rest of the modifications arise by eliminating a specific number of stops as provided by the public transport operator, and then incrementing the number of removed stops by one stop at a time, for the rest of the examined scenarios. This procedure can be applied to all the lines, and according to the layout of the line that comes as a result of the modification, a scheduling option emerges. Furthermore, each one of the examined line planning options requires a certain number of buses to perform this option. This number of vehicles required, that comes as a result of the E-VSP, is being imported as an input to the developed line planning modification model, and the optimal modification of the examined lines comes as the outcome of the formulation. The model regarding the line planning modification formulation is presented as follows:

“Given a limited fleet of electric buses B , a specific number of bus lines L and a pool of their modification options O , select the optimal line plans so that the unserved passenger demand is minimized.”

The main assumptions of the problem are the following:

1. Each line is associated with a set of modifications options, which are formed by the elimination of bus stops.
2. Each modification option requires a specific number of buses for the normal operation of the line, which is derived by solving an E-VSP problem.

Table 3
Nomenclature of the Line Planning Modification Problem.

Sets	
\mathcal{L}	set of lines examined.
\mathcal{O}	set of line modification options.
Parameters	
o_{ij}	required buses to operate line i if one chooses option j . The value of this parameter is determined by solving the E-VSP problem for option j .
d_{ij}	unserved demand for each line i if one chooses option j .
B	number of available buses.
Decision Variables	
x_{ij}	binary variables, where $x_{ij} = 1$ if we choose option j for line i , 0 otherwise.

In this problem we consider a number of lines L . For every line we propose different modification options $o \in \mathcal{O}$. Each option is developed through the elimination of bus stops. Thus, every line option has a different line length. This means that the duration of the trips, the number of stops, the charging demand of vehicles, the number of trips they conduct, and essentially the required number of vehicles change.

Considering the parameters of the problem, the E-VSP model presented above solves the vehicle scheduling problem for each one of the options per examined line and, accordingly, offers the number of vehicles required. The number of passengers not served per line modification option is $d_{i,j}$. Further, it should be clarified that the available fleet of electric buses B for solving the line planning modification is pre-determined and derived by the E-VSP.

The nomenclature of the Line Planning Modification Problem is summarized in Table 3.

The formulation of the Line Planning Modification Problem is as follows:

$$\min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{L}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{O}} x_{ij} d_{ij} \quad (49)$$

s.t.:

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{O}} x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{L} \quad (50)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{L}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{O}} x_{ij} o_{ij} \leq B \quad (51)$$

The objective function (49) aims to minimize the total number of unserved passengers due to the modification of the line plans. Constraints (50) ensure that for every examined line i , exactly one line modification option j is selected. Constraint (51) ensures that the selected line plans can be executed by the available electric buses B . The line planning modification model is a binary linear program which can be solved to global optimality. We note, though, that the input parameter values o_{ij} are determined by solving a series of E-VSP problems for every line modification option j . The combination of the line planning modification and E-VSP problems allows us to make line modifications that minimize the impact on unserved passenger demand when transitioning from a conventional to an electric bus fleet of the same size.

With both the E-VSP and line planning modification models presented in this section, the two-stage approach can be depicted in Fig. 3. For each line planning modification layout, we solve the E-VSP to obtain the required number of deployed vehicles (electric buses) and compute the operational and passenger costs. We do this for all possible line planning modification layouts, and at the end we select the layout with the best overall performance in terms of operational and passenger costs, while considering the passengers' demand in each bus stop and the size of the available fleet.

4. Case study

In our numerical experiments, we illustrate the model's application in seven bus lines across two case studies: i) one for the Athens Metropolitan area in Greece, and ii) one for the city of Limassol, Cyprus. In each bus line, we examine five different line modification options. The line modification options are based on the elimination of a different number of bus stops from the existing layout of the bus lines. The first option examined is always the existing layout of the line (number of removed stops equal to zero). The second, third, fourth and fifth options modify the line by removing a number of bus stops per direction, which is not equal to zero (i.e., removal of five to eight stops for bus lines in Athens, and removal of four to seven stops for lines in Cyprus). This number of removed stops is a parameter of the model and can be different according to the case of application. In all options, the eliminated bus stops are located in the same geographical area. This means that the bus stops removed are located at the end of each direction of the bus line. Additionally, it should be clarified that the number of stops eliminated is equal per direction. The configuration of the options, meaning the number and location of removed bus stops, has been decided according to the requirements of the public transport authority offering the services in each of the case studies (OASA for Athens, EMEL for Limassol), and are used without

Fig. 3. A flowchart of the two-stage process including the E-VSP and Line Planning Modification models.

loss of generality for our mathematical model. That is, another set of line modification options can be considered in the context of applying our method to other cities based on the respective local requirements. If in a city there are no local requirements in place, standardized approaches for generating line planning modification can be deployed (see Gkiotsalitis et al., 2019; Avila-Ordóñez et al., 2022).

We detect the best modification plan by applying the E-VSP model and the Line Planning Modification model, so that we satisfy the limitations concerning the number of vehicles available for the operation of all the bus lines examined and the passengers’ demand. We implement the vehicle scheduling problem in each line separately, but we decide on the optimal layout of the lines by applying the Line Planning Modification model for all the examined lines, with their corresponding modifications. The model presented offers the advantage of selecting the best line planning and vehicle assignment scenario that best suits the vehicle availability by the operator, but also considers the passenger demand needs. In the best-case scenario where there is an unlimited budget, the public transport operator can obtain all the electric vehicles required so that it does not need to modify the line plans resulting in unserved passenger demand. But in reality, that is rarely the case. For this reason, this model tries to balance the cost for the operator and the service provided when the resources are limited.

For every line and every scenario examined, we get as a result the required number of electric buses for the operation of the line by solving an E-VSP problem. Thus, there is a limit to the number of vehicles that are necessary to operate lines in every scenario. Each modification, according to the length of the bus line, can offer a different result, giving us the opportunity to evaluate which is the best new layout of the line while considering the number of passengers served. The lengths of the three examined lines in Athens are 15km, 20km and 28km, respectively, per direction. In the Athens case study, the first line connects areas on the west side of the Athens metropolitan area and consists of 47 bus stops per direction, and has a trip duration of approximately 66 minutes. The second line connects the north area of Athens with the south suburban area and includes 56 bus stops per direction with a trip duration of 85 minutes. The third and last line examined links the suburban regions located at the south Metropolitan area of Athens. It consists of 68 bus stops and has an average trip duration of 76 minutes. For the Limassol case study, four bus lines are examined whose lengths are 22km, 13km, 12km and 16km respectively, per direction. Bus Lines 1, 2 and 4 connect the west area of Limassol with the east. The third Bus Line, runs vertically through Limassol.

Firstly, we run the E-VSP model for the existing layout so that we can determine how many buses are required for the operation of the line if we do not make any modifications. This is considered to be the first option. Then, we execute the E-VSP model for the rest of the line modification options. All these options give us the opportunity to explore the best-case scenario for the modification of the line considering the demand of passengers and the vehicle availability for the operation of all the bus lines.

All of these cases of model application are solved using the same program code implementation of the mathematical model presented in Section 3. Python 3.12 is used, along with many of its standard libraries, while the Branch-and-Cut solution method implemented in Gurobi is used for the solution of the model. The experiments are carried out on a Lenovo ThinkSystem ST250 server equipped with an Intel Xeon E-2356G processor and 32 Gigabytes (GB) of RAM.

Fig. 4. The three bus lines examined under the case study of Athens, Greece.

4.1. Demonstration on the examined lines from Athens, Greece

The bus lines studied in this first case study of the current paper are presented in Fig. 4. The first bus line, represented by the green color, extends for about 15km and consists of 47 bus stops. Its final bus stop -considering the direction from south to north area of the line- is located at the north region and is represented by a black dot. The second line, represented by the blue color, has a length of approximately 20km and includes 56 bus stops. The final bus stop is shown by a black dot and it is located in the north area of the line. The last bus stop examined, appearing in red color, spans for about 28km and numbers 68 bus stops. The final bus stop, with direction from north to south, is located in the south area of the line and again is represented by a black dot.

All the lines serve two directions, hence we remove bus stops from the end of one direction and the beginning of the other. In other words, all the eliminated bus stops are located in the same geographical area of the line. Consequently, the length of the line changes for every modification. This results in different trip durations, charging needs, passengers served and required vehicle numbers. For each of the examined options, the trip duration changes. Specifically, the trip duration diminishes and, as a result, the energy consumed in each trip is decreased. Thus, it is possible for a bus to perform a larger number of trips compared to the current layout of the line. This means that the total required number of buses for the operation of the three bus lines is reduced when selecting line options that serve a reduced number of bus stops.

We applied our newly introduced E-VSP model for five different options for each bus line under study. These options arise from the bus stops that could be eliminated for every bus line. These modifications help us determine which is the best layout of all lines, when there is a limited number of available vehicles by the public transport operator. The model is formulated this way, so that considering the passengers' demand, the number of unserved passengers is the minimum possible. As one can notice in Tables 4 and 5, where the five different options are presented with their corresponding results from the E-VSP model, the first line modification option is the existing layout of the line. The second option modifies the line by removing five bus stops per direction. The rest of the options eliminate bus stops one by one, until the number of removed stops is eight per direction. With the first option, we can examine how many vehicles are needed to service the existing line layout. The number of stops removed by the second option is such that we can observe changes at the required number of vehicles. For the rest of the options, in which we add one stop at a time to the number of stops removed, we are trying to search for a better solution without having to remove a large number of bus stops. The results of the experiments after solving an E-VSP for every line modification option are presented below in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4

Results from the different modifications for every bus line in Athens, showcasing the number of required buses per option.

	Required buses		
	Bus Line 1	Bus Line 2	Bus Line 3
Option 1: serving all stops	14	24	22
Option 2: serving 5 less stops	13	22	22
Option 3: serving 6 less stops	12	22	21
Option 4: serving 7 less stops	12	22	20
Option 5: serving 8 less stops	12	21	19

Table 5

Results from the different modifications for every bus line in Athens, showcasing the passengers not served per option.

	Unserved Passengers		
	Bus Line 1	Bus Line 2	Bus Line 3
Option 1: serving all stops	0	0	0
Option 2: serving 5 less stops	95	68	111
Option 3: serving 6 less stops	105	93	160
Option 4: serving 7 less stops	123	134	169
Option 5: serving 8 less stops	139	169	203

One can notice that, in many cases, by just removing one more bus stop per direction, the number of vehicles required is reduced. In this case, the passengers not served are increased but the counterbalance of the minimized cost is severe when the resources are limited. For example, in the first bus line examined, we can observe that in the second modification of the line, thirteen buses are needed and in the third modification, by just adding one bus stop at the number of removed bus stops, the vehicles required are twelve. We can also make the same observation for the third line. By eliminating five bus stops, the vehicles that are necessary for the operation of the line are twenty two, but if we just remove one more bus stop, the required buses are twenty one. If we consider the fifth option, then the number of vehicles needed is nineteen, which is an important cost reduction. Similarly, for the second line examined, the results show significant changes between options 1 and 2. In the current layout, bus line 2 needs twenty four electric vehicles to operate. However, the second option requires twenty two buses and, by removing eight bus stops for the fifth option, the vehicles required are twenty-one.

When considering the unserved passenger demand, it is obvious that the more bus stops are removed, the higher the number of unserved passengers becomes. Nonetheless, in the first line examined, in options two and three, by just removing one more bus stop we manage to reduce the number of vehicles needed, from 13 to 12, and keep the number of unserved passengers low (specifically, only ten passengers are not served). The same holds true for the third line examined, where between options three and four, the number of vehicles needed is reduced, from 21 to 20, and the number of extra unserved passengers is nine.

It should be mentioned that when the existing design and layout of a line is arranged this way so that it allows the elimination of bus stops without having severe consequences on the service provided, the application of this model could be beneficial. This is the case for the third line as shown below in Fig. 5. One can notice that in the third line, the last five bus stops of a total sixty-eight, create a circular route. As one may notice, the final bus stop and the sixty-third bus stop are located very close to each other. That means that by removing the last five bus stops, we manage to decrease the number of vehicles needed and, despite not serving the passengers using these bus stops, it is safe to assume that the inconvenience for those passengers is minimal since the walking distance between these stops is very short. However, this is not the case for the second line examined. The bus stops that are candidates to be removed are scattered in larger distances from one another. This has as a result a bigger reduction on the required vehicles when applying, for example, the second option, compared to the other lines, but on the other hand increases the walking distances that passengers may have to cover. Nonetheless, there are other solutions to tackle this, which are going to be discussed in Section 5.

All these options presented in Tables 4 and 5 could be a possible modification of the existing layout of the lines, depending on the available fleet that serves the three bus lines examined. With the implementation of this two-stage model, we try to balance the cost of the electric bus fleet and the unserved passenger demand. Clearly, different numbers of available electric buses offer a different solution to our problem. Specifically, if the number of available vehicles changes, different options are selected, resulting in different line layouts, different numbers of unserved passengers, and essentially different costs for the operation of the line. This will be thoroughly discussed in Section 4.3.

As illustrated in Fig. 6, which shows the number of unserved passengers and required vehicles for every option, a reduction in the number of bus stops along the analyzed routes corresponds to a decrease in the number of vehicles required for operation. At the same time, the number of passengers not served is increased. For this reason, in our study, we implement a model that offers an optimal solution for all the lines examined, while considering a bounded fleet of electric buses and the passenger demand. This is achieved by applying the E-VSP model in every examined modification of the bus lines and deciding according to the Line Planning

Fig. 5. Layout of bus line 3 in Athens close to its final bus stop.

Table 6
Best solution of the combined line planning modification and vehicle scheduling problem for a fleet of 52 electric buses in Athens.

	Bus Line 1 Option 3	Bus Line 2 Option 5	Bus Line 3 Option 5	Total
Buses	12	21	19	52
Unserved Passengers	105	169	203	477

Modification model, which is the optimal option for all bus lines, while considering a bounded number of available vehicles that can serve all three bus lines.

In Table 6, the results of the model are presented for the case of an available fleet comprising 52 electric buses. This fleet size was chosen to present the model’s results, as the problem becomes infeasible below this threshold. In other words, the transport operator would require at least 52 vehicles to ensure the operation of the three bus lines. As one may notice, for the fleet of 52 available vehicles, in the first bus line, the third option is being selected. In Table 4, we can observe that for line 1, options 3–5 require the same number of buses, that is 12. Considering we developed the model this way so that it respects the available number of buses but also seeks for the option that minimizes the number of unserved passengers, it is reasonable that for bus line 1 it picks option 3 and not option 5. The number of passengers not served for option 3 and line 1 is 105, and the number of required buses is 12, as shown in Tables 4 and 5. For bus line 2, option 5 is being selected. The number of required buses for the operation of this layout is 21, and the passengers not served in this layout of the line is 169. Similarly, for bus line 3, the layout selected is option 5, with 203 passengers not served. The solution described above is the best solution, considering a fleet of 52 vehicles while minimizing the number of passengers not served, which in this case is 477.

In Tables 7–11, we showcase how the E-VSP model that we developed is applied in our network of the three examined bus lines. The tables present the results for every bus line, when the available fleet for our network is 52 vehicles. The results are presented for the optimal line planning solution, resulting in option 3 for bus line 1 and option 5 for bus lines 2 and 3. We applied the E-VSP model for every option of the solution, and for each bus line, we determined how many buses are needed. For every vehicle, we keep track of the energy level of the battery before and after performing any task, SOC^s and SOC^e , respectively. As mentioned in Section 3,

Fig. 6. Comparison of different options presenting the vehicles required and the number of passengers not served, in the case study of Athens, Greece.

Fig. 7. The energy level of vehicle 1 when performing its daily tasks.

a task can be a trip or a charging event that a vehicle performs during its operation. We also keep track of the time that a vehicle arrives at the node of each task, as shown in tables under the name *Arrival Time*.

For bus line 1 and option 3, that is selected in the solution of the problem for a fleet of 52 buses, as we can see in Table 7, 12 buses are required. In this table, we present how many tasks every vehicle performs, their energy levels before and after the task and the time that each task begins. For example, vehicle 1 performs 12 tasks during its day of operations, where one of them is a charging event, shown as *c.e.* in Table 7. It follows the path 23 → 7 → 32 → 13 → 38 → *c.e.* → 81 → 63 → 88 → 70 → 94 → 76. Its first trip, numbered as 23, starts at 377.73 minutes. We consider midnight as 0 minutes, so consequently, 377.73 minutes is approximately 6:30 AM. The numbering of trips is not random; it is matched to the timetable given by the public transport operator. Therefore, trip number 23 is the twenty-third trip of bus line 1 starting at 6:30 in the morning.

Table 7
Results of E-VSP for bus line 1 and option 3.

	Trips													
<i>Vehicle 1</i>	23	7	32	14	38	c.e.	81	63	88	70	94	76		
<i>SOC^s</i>	341.54	316.63	291.51	266.6	241.48	204.6	341.54	316.44	291.32	266.23	241.11	216.01		
<i>SOC^e</i>	316.63	291.53	266.6	241.51	216.58	350.0	316.44	291.35	266.23	241.13	216.01	190.92		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	377.73	450.0	509.67	580.0	639.67	724.78	864.67	935.0	1004.03	1065.0	1138.38	1200.0		
<i>Vehicle 2</i>	20	5	28	c.e.	37	53	45	c.e.	105	103	110			
<i>SOC^s</i>	341.54	316.63	291.51	248.61	341.54	304.62	279.53	245.96	341.54	316.44	291.32			
<i>SOC^e</i>	316.63	291.53	266.6	350.0	316.63	279.53	254.44	350.0	316.44	291.35	266.23			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	306.45	405.0	464.67	570.0	619.67	714.67	795.0	880.0	1311.18	1380.0	1445.15			
<i>Vehicle 3</i>	39	55	46											
<i>SOC^s</i>	332.01	306.89	281.8											
<i>SOC^e</i>	306.92	281.8	256.7											
<i>Arrival Time</i>	685.0	754.67	815.0											
<i>Vehicle 4</i>	51	42	58	49	c.e.	102	109							
<i>SOC^s</i>	341.54	316.44	291.32	266.23	241.13	332.01	306.89							
<i>SOC^e</i>	316.44	291.35	266.23	241.13	350.0	306.92	281.8							
<i>Arrival Time</i>	679.67	745.0	809.67	875.0	932.91	1355.0	1415.15							
<i>Vehicle 5</i>	2	24	8	32	15	c.e.	54	47	83	65	90	72	96	78
<i>SOC^s</i>	332.01	306.89	281.99	256.87	231.96	198.39	341.54	316.44	291.32	266.23	241.11	216.02	190.9	165.8
<i>SOC^e</i>	306.92	281.99	256.89	231.96	206.86	350.0	316.44	291.35	266.23	241.14	216.02	190.92	165.8	140.71
<i>Arrival Time</i>	330.0	397.73	470.0	529.67	595.0	680.0	739.67	835.0	904.67	970.0	1049.03	1110.0	1177.08	1250.0
<i>Vehicle 6</i>	21	c.e.	29	12	36	19	c.e.	82	64	89	71	95	77	
<i>SOC^s</i>	341.54	298.64	341.54	316.63	291.51	266.6	241.51	341.54	316.44	291.32	266.23	241.11	216.01	
<i>SOC^e</i>	316.63	350.0	316.63	291.53	266.6	241.51	350.0	316.44	291.35	266.23	241.13	216.01	190.92	
<i>Arrival Time</i>	331.83	440.0	479.67	540.0	599.67	670.0	727.91	884.67	955.0	1024.03	1090.0	1158.12	1225.0	
<i>Vehicle 7</i>	1	c.e.	26	10	34	17	c.e.	61	86	68	92	c.e.	99	
<i>SOC^s</i>	332.01	298.44	341.54	316.63	291.51	266.6	241.51	332.01	306.89	281.8	256.68	213.59	341.54	
<i>SOC^e</i>	306.92	350.0	316.63	291.53	266.6	241.51	350.0	306.92	281.8	256.7	231.58	350.0	316.44	
<i>Arrival Time</i>	300.0	390.0	433.38	505.0	569.67	635.0	692.91	895.0	964.03	1025.0	1093.77	1200.0	1261.45	
<i>Vehicle 8</i>	40	56	48	84	66	c.e.	74	98	80					
<i>SOC^s</i>	332.01	306.89	281.8	256.67	231.58	198.01	332.01	306.89	281.8					
<i>SOC^e</i>	306.92	281.8	256.7	231.58	206.49	350.0	306.92	281.8	256.7					
<i>Arrival Time</i>	705.0	769.67	855.0	924.67	990.0	1070.0	1155.0	1231.7	1300.0					
<i>Vehicle 9</i>	50	41	57	c.e.	85	67	91	73	97	79	106	104		
<i>SOC^s</i>	341.54	316.44	291.32	248.24	341.54	316.44	291.32	266.23	241.11	216.01	190.89	165.8		
<i>SOC^e</i>	316.44	291.35	266.23	350.0	316.44	291.35	266.23	241.13	216.01	190.92	165.8	140.71		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	659.67	725.0	789.67	890.0	944.67	1010.0	1074.03	1135.0	1207.08	1275.0	1335.8	1410.0		
<i>Vehicle 10</i>	22	6	30	13	c.e.	52	43	59	c.e.	101	108			
<i>SOC^s</i>	341.54	316.63	291.51	266.6	233.04	341.54	316.44	291.32	254.25	332.01	306.89			
<i>SOC^e</i>	316.63	291.53	266.6	241.51	350.0	316.44	291.35	266.23	350.0	306.92	281.8			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	357.08	430.0	494.67	560.0	640.0	699.67	765.0	829.67	915.21	1325.0	1385.15			
<i>Vehicle 11</i>	3	25	9	33	16	c.e.	44	60	c.e.	107				
<i>SOC^s</i>	332.01	306.89	281.99	256.87	231.96	198.39	332.01	306.89	269.82	341.54				
<i>SOC^e</i>	306.92	281.99	256.89	231.96	206.86	350.0	306.92	281.8	350.0	316.44				
<i>Arrival Time</i>	355.0	417.73	490.0	549.67	615.0	700.0	780.0	849.67	935.21	1360.28				
<i>Vehicle 12</i>	4	27	11	35	18	c.e.	62	87	69	93	75	100		
<i>SOC^s</i>	332.01	306.89	281.99	256.87	231.96	206.86	332.01	306.89	281.8	256.68	231.58	206.46		
<i>SOC^e</i>	306.92	281.99	256.89	231.96	206.86	350.0	306.92	281.8	256.7	231.58	206.49	181.37		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	380.0	448.9	520.0	584.67	655.0	712.91	915.0	984.15	1045.0	1113.38	1175.0	1286.45		

In Fig. 7 we present the tasks performed (trips and charging event) by vehicle 1 which serves bus line 1 when modified with option 3. As one may notice, vehicle 1 starts its operation at 377.73 min (approximately at 6:00AM, counting from midnight) by performing trip 23, with energy level 341.54kWh, which is equal to $SoC_{max} = 350kWh$ minus the energy consumption caused by the distance covered between the depot and the location of the first bus stop. As the day progresses, the energy decreases and the vehicle heads to charge, approximately for 37 minutes, to serve all the rest itineraries of the day. Vehicle 1 arrives at the charging event at 724.78 min (12:00PM), with energy level 204.6kWh. At the end of the charging event the energy level is 350.00 kWh. Then, it proceeds to perform trip no. 81 at 864.67 min, with $SoC = 341.54kWh$. As stated above, this value of SoC is equal to $SoC_{max} = 350kWh$ minus the energy consumption caused by the distance covered between the charging station (depot) and the location of the start of the bus line. Vehicle 1 concludes its daily operation by performing trip 76.

Table 8
Results (1/2) of E-VSP for bus line 2 and option 5.

	Trips												
<i>Vehicle 13</i>	25	15	39	c.e.	83	106	97	120	c.e.	162	c.e.	172	
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.12	307.0	275.95	240.66	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.95	215.98	344.83	301.36	344.83	
<i>SOC^e</i>	307.0	276.19	245.83	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	350.0	314.03	350.0	314.03	
<i>Arrival Time</i>	396.35	470.0	547.87	629.31	765.0	837.87	910.0	982.87	1065.87	1215.0	1320.0	1365.0	
<i>Vehicle 14</i>	7	31	c.e.	45	68	59	141	131	153	c.e.	167	181	
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	278.5	344.83	313.79	282.99	337.12	306.32	275.28	239.31	344.83	313.79	
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	283.67	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18	306.32	275.51	244.47	350.0	314.03	282.99	
<i>Arrival Time</i>	390.0	463.47	550.0	580.0	652.87	725.0	993.62	1070.0	1142.87	1230.0	1280.0	1363.77	
<i>Vehicle 15</i>	10	34	c.e.	51	75	89	112	c.e.	165	180			
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	278.5	344.83	313.79	272.65	241.61	205.64	344.83	313.79			
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	283.67	350.0	314.03	282.99	241.85	210.81	350.0	314.03	282.99			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	420.0	493.62	580.0	645.0	722.87	825.0	902.87	990.0	1255.0	1344.08			
<i>Vehicle 16</i>	2	27	18	61	52	76	c.e.	125	148	c.e.	160		
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	283.67	252.62	221.82	190.78	154.81	344.83	313.79	277.82	337.12		
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	283.67	252.86	221.82	191.01	159.97	350.0	314.03	282.99	350.0	306.32		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	335.0	422.55	500.0	577.87	655.0	732.87	815.87	1000.0	1074.37	1160.0	1235.58		
<i>Vehicle 17</i>	81	104	95	118	c.e.	176	171	183					
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.95	215.98	337.12	306.32	275.28					
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	350.0	306.32	275.51	244.47					
<i>Arrival Time</i>	745.0	817.87	890.0	963.62	1046.62	1265.43	1350.0	1433.32					
<i>Vehicle 18</i>	3	29	20	63	54	78	c.e.	143	133	156			
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	283.67	252.62	221.82	190.78	154.81	337.12	306.32	275.28			
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	283.67	252.86	221.82	191.01	159.97	350.0	306.32	275.51	244.47			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	350.0	442.87	520.0	602.87	675.0	752.87	835.87	1013.47	1095.0	1182.87			
<i>Vehicle 19</i>	23	12	36	49	73	c.e.	121	145	135	157			
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.12	307.0	275.95	235.49	204.45	168.48	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.95			
<i>SOC^e</i>	307.0	276.19	245.83	204.69	173.65	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	364.68	440.0	513.32	625.0	702.87	790.0	955.0	1039.07	1115.0	1197.55			
<i>Vehicle 20</i>	84	105	96	119	163	178	173						
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.95	344.83	313.79	282.99						
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	314.03	282.99	252.18						
<i>Arrival Time</i>	755.0	827.87	900.0	973.62	1225.0	1298.92	1380.0						
<i>Vehicle 21</i>	22	11	35	c.e.	65	60	103	94	117	130	155		
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.12	307.0	275.95	240.66	337.12	306.32	275.27	244.47	213.43	172.29	141.25		
<i>SOC^e</i>	307.0	276.19	245.83	350.0	306.32	275.51	244.47	213.66	182.62	141.49	110.45		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	349.08	430.0	503.47	590.0	662.87	735.0	807.87	880.0	952.87	1060.0	1167.87		
<i>Vehicle 22</i>	1	c.e.	13	37	50	74	c.e.	122	149	139	177		
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	301.36	344.83	313.79	273.33	242.29	206.32	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.94		
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	350.0	314.03	283.67	242.53	211.49	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	315.0	420.0	450.0	528.17	635.0	712.87	800.0	965.0	1084.37	1175.0	1279.83		
<i>Vehicle 23</i>	6	30	c.e.	44	67	58	102	93	116	129	152		
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	278.5	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.94	221.14	190.1	148.96	117.92		
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	283.67	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	190.33	159.29	118.16	87.12		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	380.0	452.87	540.0	570.0	642.87	715.0	792.1	870.0	942.87	1045.0	1128.47		
<i>Vehicle 24</i>	41	64	55	79	c.e.	124	147	137	159				
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.95	215.98	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.95				
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14				
<i>Arrival Time</i>	530.0	612.87	685.0	762.87	970.0	985.0	1064.37	1145.0	1221.35				
<i>Vehicle 25</i>	5	17	40	85	108	99	c.e.	168	182				
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	297.44	266.4	344.83	313.79	282.99	252.18	344.83	313.79				
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	266.64	236.27	314.03	282.99	252.18	350.0	314.03	282.99				
<i>Arrival Time</i>	370.0	490.0	562.87	785.0	857.87	935.0	1280.0	1295.0	1388.32				
<i>Vehicle 26</i>	21	9	33	c.e.	48	72	c.e.	90	113	c.e.	128	151	140
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.12	307.0	275.95	240.66	344.83	313.79	277.82	344.83	313.79	277.82	344.83	313.79	282.99
<i>SOC^e</i>	307.0	276.19	245.83	350.0	314.03	282.99	350.0	314.03	282.99	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18
<i>Arrival Time</i>	329.08	410.0	482.87	570.0	615.0	692.87	780.0	835.0	912.87	1000.0	1035.0	1113.92	1190.0

Table 9
Results (2/2) of E-VSP for bus line 2 and option 5.

	Trips													
<i>Vehicle 27</i>	8	32	c.e.	47	71	c.e.	87	110	c.e.	127	150	c.e.	164	179
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	278.5	344.83	313.79	277.82	344.83	313.79	277.82	344.83	313.79	277.82	344.83	313.79
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	283.67	350.0	314.03	282.99	350.0	314.03	282.99	350.0	314.03	282.99	350.0	314.03	282.99
<i>Arrival Time</i>	400.0	472.72	560.0	605.0	682.87	770.0	805.0	882.87	970.0	1025.0	1099.22	1190.0	1240.0	1319.08
<i>Vehicle 28</i>	4	28	19	62	53	77	91	114	c.e.	166	174			
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	283.67	252.62	221.82	190.78	149.64	118.6	82.637	344.83	297.44			
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	283.67	252.86	221.82	191.01	159.97	118.84	87.8	350.0	314.03	266.64			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	360.0	432.87	510.0	592.87	665.0	742.87	845.0	922.87	1010.0	1265.0	1395.0			
<i>Vehicle 29</i>	24	14	38	c.e.	84	107	98	142	132	154				
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.12	307.0	275.95	240.66	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.94	221.14	190.1				
<i>SOC^e</i>	307.0	276.19	245.83	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	190.33	159.29				
<i>Arrival Time</i>	380.58	460.0	538.02	775.0	847.87	920.0	991.09	1003.62	1080.0	1152.72				
<i>Vehicle 30</i>	24	14	38	c.e.	84	107	98	142	132	154				
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.12	307.0	275.95	240.66	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.94	221.14	190.1				
<i>SOC^e</i>	307.0	276.19	245.83	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	190.33	159.29				
<i>Arrival Time</i>	380.58	460.0	538.02	775.0	847.87	920.0	991.09	1003.62	1080.0	1152.72				
<i>Vehicle 31</i>	86	109	100	144	134									
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.94	221.14									
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	190.33									
<i>Arrival Time</i>	795.0	867.87	945.0	1023.47	1105.0									
<i>Vehicle 32</i>	42	65	56	80	c.e.	123	146	136	158					
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.95	215.98	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.95					
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	350.0	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14					
<i>Arrival Time</i>	545.0	622.87	695.0	772.87	855.87	975.0	1054.22	1130.0	1207.1					
<i>Vehicle 33</i>	43	66	57	80	92	115	c.e.	161	169	183				
<i>SOC^s</i>	344.83	313.79	282.99	251.94	221.14	190.1	154.13	344.83	297.44	266.4				
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.03	282.99	252.18	221.14	190.33	159.29	350.0	314.03	266.64	235.6				
<i>Arrival Time</i>	555.0	632.87	705.0	782.87	855.0	932.87	1015.87	1205.0	1315.0	1408.32				

In Fig. 8 we can observe the locations of the charging facilities corresponding to each bus line examined in this problem. Essentially, these locations correspond to the locations of the depots for our network. The green dot represents the depot charging location of bus line 1. The blue dot of bus line 2 and the red one of bus line 3. All vehicles start their operation fully charged, meaning that their energy level at the depot is 350 kWh. Vehicle 1 starts its first trip, number 23 with a battery level of $SOC^s = 341.54$ kWh. The difference between 350 kWh and 341.54 kWh equals to the energy consumption caused by the distance covered between the depot (green dot) and the location of the start of the bus line. The energy level of the bus after performing trip 23 is $SOC^e = 316.63$ kWh. As we can observe from Table 7, vehicle 1 returns to the first bus stop after performing trip 23 and proceeds to perform trip 7. Consequently, the energy level at the first bus stop of trip 7, $SOC^s = 316.63$ kWh, is equal to the energy level at the end of trip 23. After performing trip 38 the vehicle heads to the corresponding depot for charging at 724.78 minutes, approximately after 6 and a half hours of operation. Its energy state when it arrives at the charging depot is 204.6 kWh and after the charging procedure it reaches its full capacity, 350 kWh. In our model we assumed that the minimum energy level for the operation of the lines is 70 kWh. That means that they do not necessarily reach their minimum energy limit when they head for charging. Hence, vehicle 1 and many other vehicles of our network head to the depot for charging with battery level higher than 70 kWh.

It should also be clarified that when a vehicle is charged, the charging time slot is fully occupied by the vehicle, regardless of the actual charging duration. That is, the corresponding charger is considered occupied for the entire duration of the time slot even if the bus finishes charging some minutes before the end of the time slot. This helps us match the vehicle to the corresponding charger according to the timetable of the line and the charging timetable, allowing the realistic modeling of charging queues.

As mentioned in Section 3.1, we are handling the scheduling procedure in slices, so in some cases the vehicles start the time-slice fully charged. This is also the case for vehicle 1. The time slices are a way to handle computational difficulties of the NP-Hard E-VSP problem that arise from the complexity of the possible connection between tasks. To avoid having small time slices that might result in myopic solutions, the duration of each slice is large (approximately, 6.5 hours). The selection of the 6.5 hours coincides with the time of a bus driver’s shift without his/her daily break, as provided by the transport operator. This way, a vehicle corresponds to a driver and after the end of a time slice it either heads to the depot or stays at the last bus stop. In the next time slice, vehicles start their trips from the location they were at the end of the previous time slice. In the case of vehicle 1, it heads to the depot for charging at the end of the first time slice and then goes to the first bus stop from the depot to perform trip 81.

As we can observe in Tables 7–11, in many cases, vehicles after finishing a trip that finishes at the terminal of the line, they proceed to perform the immediately following trip with direction from the terminal to the starting point. In this case, the energy level of the bus at the end of the trip is equal to the energy state of the bus at the start of the following trip. However, as we can see in Table 8, vehicle 19 after performing trip 36 has energy level $SOC^e = 245.83$ kWh and at the beginning of the following trip 49 its

Table 10
Results (1/2) of E-VSP for bus line 3 and option 5.

		Trips											
<i>Vehicle 34</i>	105	86	120	101	150	133	159						
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32	235.24	210.06	182.98						
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15	210.06	184.88	157.8						
<i>Arrival Time</i>	852.67	920.0	1017.67	1085.0	1151.87	1220.0	1285.28						
<i>Vehicle 35</i>	25	8	37	c.e.	83	116	97	147	131	157	139		
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	311.86	284.78	244.76	337.89	310.81	285.63	258.54	233.36	206.28	181.1		
<i>SOC^e</i>	311.86	286.68	256.87	350.0	312.71	285.63	260.45	233.36	208.18	181.1	155.92		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	431.87	500.0	567.67	660.01	895.0	972.67	1040.0	1122.35	1190.0	1261.08	1320.0		
<i>Vehicle 36</i>	2	27	11	c.e.	45	76	56	110	91	123			
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.89	310.81	282.9	246.04	337.89	310.81	285.63	258.54	233.36	206.28			
<i>SOC^e</i>	312.71	282.9	257.72	350.0	312.71	285.63	260.45	233.36	208.18	181.1			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	390.0	456.87	525.0	630.0	700.0	767.67	835.0	907.67	975.0	1042.67			
<i>Vehicle 37</i>	62	42	c.e.	79	59	113	94						
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	314.59	277.73	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32						
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.59	289.41	350.0	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.14						
<i>Arrival Time</i>	597.67	665.0	760.0	802.67	870.0	942.67	1010.0						
<i>Vehicle 38</i>	24	9	38	c.e.	107	87	118	99	c.e.	165	162		
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	311.86	284.78	244.76	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32	237.15	339.77	314.59		
<i>SOC^e</i>	311.86	286.68	256.87	350.0	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15	7	350.0	314.59	289.41	
<i>Arrival Time</i>	406.4	505.0	572.67	665.01	872.67	935.0	997.67	1065.0	1123.1	1329.5	1410.0		
<i>Vehicle 39</i>	1	28	13	c.e.	70	49	81	c.e.	126	155	139		
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.89	310.81	282.9	246.04	339.77	314.59	287.5	247.49	337.89	310.81	285.63		
<i>SOC^e</i>	312.71	282.9	257.72	350.0	314.59	289.41	259.6	350.0	312.71	285.63	260.45		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	365.0	461.87	550.0	650.0	702.67	765.0	827.67	920.01	1125.0	1236.08	1320.0		
<i>Vehicle 40</i>	3	31	14	65	74	54	c.e.	145	129	158	161		
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.89	310.81	282.9	255.81	212.89	187.71	150.85	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32		
<i>SOC^e</i>	312.71	282.9	257.72	230.63	187.71	162.54	350.0	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	400.0	502.67	570.0	632.67	742.67	805.0	910.0	1097.67	1165.0	1275.6	1380.0		
<i>Vehicle 41</i>	63	43	73	54	c.e.	125	152	135					
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32	225.46	337.89	310.81	285.63					
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15	350.0	312.71	310.81	285.63					
<i>Arrival Time</i>	607.67	675.0	737.67	810.0	900.0	1110.0	1196.08	1255.0					
<i>Vehicle 42</i>	22	29	c.e.	40	71	51	c.e.	144	128	154	141		
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	294.12	254.11	337.89	310.81	285.63	248.76	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32		
<i>SOC^e</i>	311.86	266.22	350.0	312.71	285.63	260.45	350.0	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15		
<i>Arrival Time</i>	375.28	482.5	580.0	640.0	717.67	785.0	880.0	1082.67	1150.0	1221.08	1350.0		
<i>Vehicle 43</i>	39	69	50	82	114	95	125	163					
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.89	310.81	285.63	258.54	208.3	183.12	146.26	339.77					
<i>SOC^e</i>	312.71	285.63	260.45	230.63	183.12	157.94	350.0	314.59					
<i>Arrival Time</i>	635.0	697.67	770.0	832.67	952.67	1020.0	1110.0	1304.65					
<i>Vehicle 44</i>	26	10	c.e.	68	48	80	60	c.e.	143	127	153	137	
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	311.86	275.0	339.77	314.59	287.5	259.6	222.73	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32	
<i>SOC^e</i>	311.86	286.68	350.0	314.59	289.41	259.6	234.42	350.0	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15	
<i>Arrival Time</i>	436.55	525.0	620.0	677.67	745.0	812.67	880.0	965.07	1067.67	1135.0	1216.08	1290.0	
<i>Vehicle 45</i>	61	41	72	52	c.e.	146	130	156	140				
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32	225.46	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32				
<i>SOC^e</i>	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15	350.0	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15				
<i>Arrival Time</i>	587.67	655.0	722.67	790.0	890.0	1102.67	1175.0	1251.08	1350.0				

energy level is $SOC^s = 235.49$ kWh. This indicates that vehicle 19, after performing trip 36 with direction from the starting point to the terminal, proceeds to serve trip 49 with the same direction. For this reason, we observe the difference in the energy levels at the end of the trip 36 and the beginning of the trip 49, since vehicle 19 has to cover the distance between the last and first stop, but in an out-of-service state for passengers. This decision of the model actually leads to the reduction of buses needed for the operation of the network, considering the objective function we implemented.

The results, as presented in this section, showcase the best solution for our problem of electric vehicle scheduling and line planning, when considering a fleet of 52 buses. The fleet of 52 buses is the worst-case scenario, where below this number of vehicles the problem is infeasible. Under this scenario, the layout of bus line 1 is modified this way so that the last 6 stops are eliminated, 12 buses are required for the operation of the line and 105 passengers are not served. Bus line 2 is modified this way so that 8 bus stops are

Table 11
Results (2/2) of E-VSP for bus line 3 and option 5.

	Trips												
<i>Vehicle 46</i>	5	33	16	67	47	78	58	112	93	102			
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.89	310.81	282.9	255.81	230.63	203.55	178.37	151.28	126.1	89.24			
<i>SOC^c</i>	312.71	282.9	257.72	230.63	205.45	178.37	153.19	126.1	100.92	350.0			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	455.0	527.67	595.0	657.67	725.0	792.67	860.0	932.67	1000.0	1090.0			
<i>Vehicle 47</i>	6	34	17	c.e.	109	90	121	102	151	136			
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.89	310.81	282.9	257.72	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32	235.24	210.06			
<i>SOC^c</i>	312.71	282.9	257.72	350.0	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15	210.06	184.88			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	455.0	532.67	600.0	658.1	892.67	960.0	1022.67	1090.0	1170.92	1260.0			
<i>Vehicle 48</i>	20	4	29	13	c.e.	84	115	96	c.e.	166			
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	311.86	284.78	256.87	220.01	337.89	310.81	285.63	248.76	339.77			
<i>SOC^c</i>	311.86	286.68	256.87	231.69	350.0	312.71	285.63	260.45	350.0	314.59			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	340.28	410.0	482.5	550.0	640.0	900.0	962.67	1030.0	1120.0	1359.5			
<i>Vehicle 49</i>	21	c.e.	33	15	66	46	77	57	111	92	124	c.e.	165
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	299.75	339.77	311.86	284.77	259.59	232.51	207.33	180.24	155.06	127.98	90.69	339.77
<i>SOC^c</i>	311.86	350.0	311.86	286.68	259.59	234.41	207.33	182.15	155.06	129.88	102.8	350.0	314.59
<i>Arrival Time</i>	370.77	470.0	507.67	575.0	647.67	715.0	782.67	850.0	917.67	985.0	1057.67	1143.71	1329.33
<i>Vehicle 50</i>	64	44	75	55	108	89	122	103					
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32	235.24	210.06	182.98	157.8					
<i>SOC^c</i>	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15	210.06	184.88	157.8	132.62					
<i>Arrival Time</i>	622.67	690.0	757.67	825.0	887.67	955.0	1037.67	1105.0					
<i>Vehicle 51</i>	23	c.e.	38	19	c.e.	106	88	119	100	149	134	160	
<i>SOC^s</i>	339.77	299.75	339.77	311.86	286.68	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32	235.24	210.06	182.98	
<i>SOC^c</i>	311.86	350.0	311.86	286.68	350.0	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15	210.06	184.88	157.8	
<i>Arrival Time</i>	401.4	500.0	552.67	620.0	1299.97	867.67	940.0	1002.67	1070.0	1146.72	1230.0	1299.97	
<i>Vehicle 52</i>	7	35	18	c.e.	104	85	117	98	148	132			
<i>SOC^s</i>	337.89	310.81	282.9	257.72	339.77	314.59	287.5	262.32	235.24	210.06			
<i>SOC^c</i>	312.71	282.9	257.72	350.0	314.59	289.41	262.32	237.15	210.06	184.88			
<i>Arrival Time</i>	480.0	547.67	615.0	673.1	847.67	915.0	982.67	1050.0	1122.35	1200.0			

removed and 169 passengers are not served and bus line 3 is also altered by eliminating 8 bus stops and 203 passengers are not served. In Section 4.3, we present a sensitivity analysis of the results when we examine this problem for a range of available number of vehicles.

4.2. Demonstration on the examined lines from Limassol, Cyprus

The bus lines studied in the case study of Limassol, Cyprus, along with their corresponding charging station are presented in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, respectively. The first bus line, represented by the magenta color, extends for approximately 22km and consists of 46 bus stops. Its final bus stop, considering the direction from west to east, is located at the east region and is represented by a black dot. The second line, represented by the blue color, has a length of approximately 13km and includes 34 bus stops. The final bus stop is shown by a black dot and it is located in the east area of the line. The last bus stop of the third line, which extends for approximately 12km, consists of 29 stops and is represented by yellow color, is in the same location of the final bus stop of the second bus line. The fourth bus line, represented by red color, exceeds for 16km and consists of 32 stops. The final bus stop of the fourth bus line is the same as the one of the first bus line's.

The examined bus lines serve two directions, hence we remove bus stops from the end of one direction and the beginning of the other. Therefore, all the eliminated bus stops are located in the same geographical area of the line. This means that the length of the line changes for every modification, depending on the number of eliminated stops. As mentioned above, this leads to diminished trip durations, charging needs, passengers served and required vehicle numbers.

For this case study we applied the developed E-VSP model for a different set of options, compared to the ones of the first case study. Specifically, we implement five options-modifications as in the first case study, however a different number of bus stops is eliminated. For the first option the bus line layout remain as is, for the second option four bus stops are removed. For the rest of the options, we eliminate bus stops one by one, until the number of removed stops is seven per direction. One may notice in Tables 12 and 13, the different options with their corresponding results from the E-VSP model.

As in the case study of Athens, the results for the case study of Limassol, confirm that in most of the cases just by eliminating four bus stops (option 2), we get to see a reduction in the required number of vehicles. For example, for the operation of the first bus line without any modifications, 23 buses are required. However, if we implement the first option, the E-VSP model indicates that 22 vehicles are required. Similarly, in Bus Line 3, the number of required vehicles is diminished with the implementation of option 3, from five buses to four.

Fig. 8. Charging locations corresponding to each bus line in Athens, Greece.

Table 12

Results from the different modifications for every bus line in Limassol showcasing the number of required buses per option.

	Required buses			
	Bus Line 1	Bus Line 2	Bus Line 3	Bus Line 4
Option 1: serving all stops	23	5	5	9
Option 2: serving 4 less stops	22	4	5	8
Option 3: serving 5 less stops	22	4	4	8
Option 4: serving 6 less stops	22	4	4	8
Option 5: serving 7 less stops	22	4	4	8

Table 13

Results from the different modifications for every bus line in Limassol showcasing the passengers not served per option.

	Unserved Passengers			
	Bus Line 1	Bus Line 2	Bus Line 3	Bus Line 4
Option 1: serving all stops	0	0	0	0
Option 2: serving 4 less stops	53	61	104	63
Option 3: serving 5 less stops	83	95	111	68
Option 4: serving 6 less stops	106	105	160	93
Option 5: serving 7 less stops	122	123	169	134

Fig. 9. Examined bus lines in Limassol, Cyprus.

Table 14

Best solution of the combined line planning modification and vehicle scheduling problem for a fleet of 38 electric buses, in the case study of Limassol.

	Bus Line 1 Option 2	Bus Line 2 Option 3	Bus Line 3 Option 2	Bus Line 4 Option 2	Total
Buses	22	4	4	8	38
Unservd Passengers	53	111	61	63	288

In Fig. 11, one may notice the results from the different options, concerning the number of required vehicles and the passengers not served, for every option-modification of the four examined lines. In Table 14, we present the results of our two-stage approach for the examined network, for the case of 38 available buses. In more detail, for Bus Line 1, option 2 is selected which modifies the line by eliminating four stops and results in 53 unserved passengers. For Bus Line 2, option 3 is selected, in which 5 stops are removed and 111 passengers are not served. Bus Line 3 is modified by eliminating four bus stops, resulting to 61 passengers not served and Bus Line 4, altered by option 2, does not meet the demand of 63 passengers. In total, the number of the passengers not served in this network for the case of a fleet size equal to 38 buses, is 288. The 38 vehicles is actually the benchmark of feasibility for the Limassol network. Below this number, the model can not retrieve a solution. The upper benchmark, in which the lines do not require modification is 42 buses.

The results of the Limassol case study showcase the transferability of the developed model to other networks than the first case study of Athens. Specifically, the model implemented in Limassol, behaves as expected and for the different options the number of required vehicles diminishes. It is worth mentioning that the set of options in this case study differentiates from the ones in the Athens network, therefore, except from its transferability we conclude that the model can be generalizable for the case of different sets of options.

Fig. 10. Examined bus lines and their charging location in Limassol, Cyprus.

Fig. 11. Comparison of different options presenting the vehicles required and the number of passengers not served, in the case study of Limassol, Cyprus.

Table 15
Selected options of the examined lines for a range of available vehicles.

	Options Bus Line 1	Options Bus Line 2	Options Bus Line 3	Available Buses	Required Buses	Total number of unserved passengers		Options Bus Line 1	Options Bus Line 2	Options Bus Line 3
Buses	[1, 3] = 12	[2, 5] = 21	[3, 5] = 19	52	52	477	Passengers	[1, 3] = 105	[2, 5] = 169	[3, 5] = 203
Buses	[1, 3] = 12	[2, 2] = 22	[3, 5] = 19	53	53	376	Passengers	[1, 3] = 105	[2, 2] = 68	[3, 5] = 203
Buses	[1, 3] = 12	[2, 2] = 22	[3, 4] = 20	54	54	342	Passengers	[1, 3] = 105	[2, 2] = 68	[3, 4] = 169
Buses	[1, 1] = 14	[2, 2] = 22	[3, 5] = 19	55	55	271	Passengers	[1, 1] = 0	[2, 2] = 68	[3, 5] = 203
Buses	[1, 3] = 12	[2, 2] = 22	[3, 1] = 22	56	56	173	Passengers	[1, 3] = 105	[2, 2] = 68	[3, 1] = 0
Buses	[1, 2] = 13	[2, 2] = 22	[3, 1] = 22	57	57	163	Passengers	[1, 2] = 95	[2, 2] = 68	[3, 1] = 0
Buses	[1, 1] = 14	[2, 2] = 22	[3, 1] = 22	58	58	68	Passengers	[1, 1] = 0	[2, 2] = 68	[3, 1] = 0
Buses	[1, 1] = 14	[2, 2] = 22	[3, 1] = 22	59	58	68	Passengers	[1, 1] = 0	[2, 2] = 68	[3, 1] = 0
Buses	[1, 1] = 14	[2, 1] = 24	[3, 1] = 22	60	60	0	Passengers	[1, 1] = 0	[2, 1] = 0	[3, 1] = 0
Buses	[1, 1] = 14	[2, 1] = 24	[3, 1] = 22	66	60	0	Passengers	[1, 1] = 0	[2, 1] = 0	[3, 1] = 0

Fig. 12. Graphic representation of the number of passengers not served when considering a range of available vehicles.

4.3. Sensitivity analysis

In this section, we provide a sensitivity analysis concerning the behavior of our model when the size of the available fleet changes, for the Athens case study. We study how the model reacts to different numbers of available vehicles, which option is selected for every bus line in each case, and how that affects the number of unserved passengers. The analysis ranges from the benchmark of 52 vehicles, where below this point the model is infeasible, until the increase of the fleet size does not have an impact on the number of unserved passengers. This is the case when the available fleet is greater than 60 vehicles.

In Table 15, one can observe which modification of the layout of the lines is selected for every fleet size available, how many buses are required for the operation of the network, and how many passengers are not served due to the elimination of bus stops. For example, for an available fleet of 52 buses, one may observe that in bus line 1 the 3rd option is selected [1,3], in which the number of required vehicles so that this modification of the line (option 3) handles all the itineraries, is 12 ([1,3] = 12, where 1 stands for bus line 1, 3 for the 3rd option and 12 for the buses). Similarly, for bus line 2, [2,5] = 21, option 5 is selected, which requires 21 buses. The same logic applies for the number of passengers unserved, where in the case of line 1 option 3 [1,3] is 105 and in the case of line 2 option 5 [2,5] is 169. Naturally, the greater the number of the buses in the fleet, the fewer the passengers that are not served. For a fleet consisting of 57 vehicles, we can see that for bus line 1 option 2 is selected, which indicates that 13 buses are required for the operation of this line, 5 bus stops are eliminated from the layout of the line, and 95 passengers are not served. For bus line 2, option 2 is selected where 22 buses are required and 68 passengers are not served. Lastly, for bus line 3 option 1 is selected indicating that no bus stops are eliminated and 22 buses are required. In total, the solution indicates that 57 buses are required for the operation of the network, which is equal to all the available vehicles.

An interesting finding occurs for the case of 59 available vehicles. As we can see, the buses required for the operation of the network are 58 even if we have 59 buses available. In closer inspection, the 59th vehicle is not used because bus line 2 requires 24 buses for its operation without any modification. As one can observe, for the operation of the network without any modifications on the layouts of the lines, 60 buses are required. Beyond this point, increasing the size of the fleet does not play a role in the layout

Fig. 13. Graphic representation of the number of required buses and the number of passengers not served considering the size of the available fleet for every bus line examined.

Fig. 14. Graphic representation of the number of passengers not served in our network in comparison with the size of the available fleet.

of the bus lines. An interesting trade-off emerges when one selects a fleet of 56 buses, which reduces the unserved demand by 304 passengers by purchasing 4 additional buses compared to the case of deploying 52 buses.

Fig. 12 offers a visual representation of how the availability of vehicles affects the number of unserved passengers. The figure shows that for a small fleet, the number of unserved passengers is higher compared to the case of larger fleet sizes. As one can observe, the selection of options for one bus line, therefore the number of unserved passengers, is not independent of the selection of options for the other lines. For example, for the case of 55 vehicles, bus line 1 serves all passengers, indicating that the model selects option 1. However, bus line 3 serves fewer passengers compared to the case of the fleet of 54 vehicles and bus line 2 serves the same number of passengers for both cases. For the case of 56 available vehicles, bus lines 1 and 3 follow the exact opposite pattern compared to the case of 55 vehicles.

Fig. 13 shows that if we have more available vehicles, these vehicles will be distributed to the different lines to reduce the total number of unserved passengers. This distribution of the extra vehicles to the bus lines is not even, as the extra vehicles are distributed so as to satisfy as much passenger demand as possible. One can also observe the relationship between the number of passengers not served and the vehicles used in the examined network in Fig. 14.

5. Concluding remarks

The study proposes a novel mathematical optimization model for the combined line planning modification and vehicle scheduling problem of electric buses, which considers charging scheduling constraints. The model considers the demand of passengers at each bus stop of the examined lines, the deadheading time between the final stop of their trip and the depot, and the delay time due to the charging of buses. We implement a two-stage approach on the solution of this problem. We first schedule the fleet for each modification of the layout of the bus lines examined. These modifications, as mentioned above, arise from the elimination of bus stops, while the data concerning the number of routes, frequencies etc. are regarded the same for all the options. To this end, we formulated the (Vehicle Scheduling Problem) for electric buses (E-VSP), while taking into account the charging needs of the vehicles, timetable of the line, the autonomy of the buses, the number of trips performed per day, the trip distances, and the deadheading distances. The result from the first stage of the problem is the number of vehicles required for the lines to operate in each modification. These data serve as input to the second stage of our approach. The line planning modification problem for electric buses, which aims to

select the optimal bus line layout and minimize the number of unserved passengers, when there is a bounded number of available vehicles. Since, the number of buses could be limited, the need for modifications of the layout might emerge. As stated in the previous sections, eliminating bus stops leads to reduction of the length of the examined bus lines and therefore, reduction of required vehicles. Evidently, the outcome of this two-stage model provides a balanced solution that optimizes the operational costs of electric buses under resource constraints while meeting passenger transportation demands for every examined option.

Following the problem formulation, the model is applied in seven bus lines: three from the bus line network of Athens, and four from Limassol, Cyprus. We implement a model that offers the best solution for all the lines examined, while considering a bounded fleet of electric buses and the passenger demand. This is achieved by applying the E-VSP model in every examined modification of the bus lines and deciding according to the Line Planning Modification model which is the optimal option for all bus lines, while considering a bounded number of available vehicles that can serve all three bus lines. In the case study of Athens, we showed that with significant line modifications resulting in 477 unserved passengers one can offer a service by using only 52 electric buses. Increasing the available number of electric buses to 56 will result in only 173 unserved passengers, whereas increasing this number further to 60 electric buses will allow us to operate all lines without performing any modifications resulting in 0 unserved passengers. Here, it is worth highlighting that a conventional fleet of non-electric vehicles could operate all three bus lines without requiring any line modifications with 17 buses less (43 instead of 60). Furthermore, in the case of Limassol, we concluded that for the minimum possible number of utilized vehicles, which is 38, the examined network can not serve 288 passengers. However, if we do not modify the examined lines, 42 buses are required. One may assume that, for larger sizes of the available fleet in Limassol than the benchmark of 38 vehicles, the number of passengers unserved can be diminished from 288. The results mentioned above indicate the trade-off between the operational cost (number of e-buses required) and the satisfaction of the passenger demand.

Considering the assumptions of our model and the respective limitations, future research directions could include the consideration of more examined bus lines on a larger network. Additionally, future studies could explore the challenges of synchronizing modified electric bus routes with other operator-provided transportation modes, such as electric scooters, minibuses, and bicycles, which facilitate first/last-mile trip legs of passengers. Building on this, another promising research direction involves the development of dynamic scheduling algorithms that optimize electric buses dispatched in real-time, accounting for fluctuations in micro-mobility availability, passenger demand, and energy constraints.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marilena Merakou: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft; **Dimitrios Rizopoulos:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing; **Konstantinos Gkiotsalitis:** Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of competing interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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